

Comparative Study

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A comparison study of cognitive deficits in radiologically and clinically isolated syndromes

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Abstract

Up until now, no information has existed regarding a comparison of the pattern and frequency of cognitive deficits between radiologically isolated syndrome (RIS) and clinically isolated syndrome (CIS) patients. Within this objective, Rao's Brief Repeatable Battery and Stroop test were administered to 28 RIS patients, 25 CIS patients, and 22 healthy controls.

Conclusions: The prevalence of cognitive deficits in RIS was similar to that of CIS. Cognitive deficits seem to be present in RIS patients regardless of the presence of risk factors for a future symptomatic demyelinating event.

Keywords: Clinically isolated syndrome; cognitive impairment; demyelinating disease; depression; information processing speed; radiologically isolated syndrome.